

AXIOMS OF ISAAC ASIMOV'S CONCEPT OF PSYCHOHISTORY: SCIENCE FICTION AND REALITY

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Abstract. This paper presents the results of the analysis of socio-philosophical problems of the concept of “psychohistory”. The concept plays an important role in the development of storyline and thematic component in the “Foundation” novels by famous American science fiction writer Isaac Asimov. Before being thoroughly studied, the ideas of Isaac Asimov were not taken seriously by literary authorities, but soon after they got the full focus of the entire world community (scientists, literary critics, sociologists, historians, etc.), they became the prototype of real-life scientific concepts (psychohistory, cliodynamics, robotics), and also gave rise to a whole series of books written on the basis of the concept of psychohistory.

Key words: Asimov, science fiction, “Foundation”, plot, theme, psychohistory, concept, cliodynamics, axiom.

ФАНТАСТИЧНОСТЬ И РЕАЛЬНОСТЬ АКСИОМ КОНЦЕПЦИИ ПСИХОИСТОРИИ АЙЗЕКА АЗИМОВА

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Аннотация. В настоящей статье приводятся результаты анализа социально-философской проблематики концепции «психоистории», играющей важнейшую роль в развитии сюжетной линии и тематической составляющей цикла романов «Основание» американского писателя-фантаста

Айзека Азимова. Идеи Айзека Азимова, первоначально никем не воспринятые серьёзно, по мере их изучения заинтересовали всю мировую общественность (включая ученых, литературоведов, социологов, историков и др.), они стали прообразом реально существующих научных концепций (психоистория, клиодинамика, робототехника), а также породили целую серию книг, написанных на основе концепции психоистории.

Ключевые слова: Азимов, научная фантастика, «Основание», сюжет, тема, психоистория, концепция, клиодинамика, аксиома.

Introduction. In his large-scale Foundation cycle, the American science fiction writer Isaac Asimov thought about how science will change and what new disciplines will appear in the future. On the pages of the novels of his cycle, the writer created a new science – psychohistory. Psychohistory is a fictional science, the essence of which is the application of complex mathematical calculations to the political, social and economic processes in society, which makes it possible to predict the future with a high degree of accuracy [1, p. 3]. This fictional science has inspired many scientists. Many studies have been carried out, articles and books have been written; at the same time, the literary and popular science heritage of Isaac Asimov has not yet been fully disclosed, scientists and literary critics are still trying to understand the diversity of the writer's work.

Axioms of psychohistory. The idea to create psychohistory came to Isaac Asimov's mind in the 1940s and 1950s years of the 20th century. The constant wars and other upheavals that engulf humanity year after year have led people to want stability. Naturally, this need was instantly realized in literature – countless works of various kinds and content appeared exactly at that time. Isaac Asimov was no exception, but the concept of psychohistory was somewhat different from anything that was available on the book market of that epoch. Inspired by Edward Gibbon's "The Decline and Fall of the Roman Empire", the writer began to contemplate the possibility of predicting the future in the long term with a high degree of accuracy, which would prevent most upcoming crises [2, p. 26]. Being a scientist, fired up with

the idea, the science fiction writer tried to project his thoughts onto science and soon noticed that many processes in society can be predicted using the mathematical model of the molecular kinetic theory of gases. By combining his thoughts with those of Edward Gibbon, Isaac Asimov had a working conceptual model capable of predicting the future with high accuracy. However, the writer had to immediately make several important reservations, which later became the axioms of a newly created concept:

1. The number of people involved in the historical process must be large enough for the results of statistical calculations to be reliable. The first axiom is an attempt by the science fiction writer to point out the statistical nature of psychohistory as a mathematical theory. Isaac Asimov formulates one of the fundamental principles for constructing a future theory. In his works, the apparatus of the theory of differential equations is taken as a basis. However, the stated theory of ethnogenesis has a hidden statistical character.

2. People should be ignorant of the existence of psychohistory and therefore should know nothing of its predictions; and then the knowledge of the future will not pervert their conduct. The second axiom formulates a principle that should resolve the confrontation between logic and freedom. This is a justification for the right of psychohistory to exist as a theory that governs society and gives people the freedom to change the society in which they live, and which no longer suits them. But that is precisely what Hari Seldon created psychohistory for.

3. Humans are the only sentient beings in the galaxy. The third axiom, on the contrary, is not a justification of the right of psychohistory to exist, but an indication of the reason that can prevent this. In the 1980s, cosmologists and philosophers (whose interests are focused on the issue of extraterrestrial civilizations) began to vigorously discuss ideas related to the anthropological principle. This principle spoke of the privileged place occupied in the universe by the anthropomorphic form of mind to which man belongs. How solid is this claim? We believe that here we should pay attention to the fact that the anthropological principle has the status of a general scientific one, because it links together the global properties of the Universe

with a set of conditions in which the emergence of life and mind is possible [3, p. 52].

Here, in our opinion, it is necessary to make one more important clarification - the model itself, or rather one of its primary sources, imposes restrictions on the scale of forecasting: it is impossible to predict people's actions, like the movement of individual gas molecules, and therefore the concept made it possible to predict only social processes, and not individual actions of people. It turns out the idea of creating and developing a society whose progress is planned in advance and is not subject to random changes. At first glance, this seems like a utopia and is by no means feasible in reality.

Psychohistory in the “Foundation” novels. One of these large-scale works of Isaac Asimov is the “Foundation”, a series of seven science fiction novels. The action of the cycle takes place in the distant future. The writer places the characters in various situations, describing his idea in more detail. The development of a science capable of predicting the future of society and manipulating it was carried out by scientists Hari Seldon and Yugo Amaryl. Based on the results of their research, they began to develop a science capable of predicting the long-term future using a high-precision complex mathematical model. After the completion of the work, it turned out that the forecast regarding the future of the Galactic Empire is not comforting – in five centuries it will inevitably collapse, and its citizens will experience a period of barbarism, which can drag on for a long time. However, thanks to the same psychohistory, Hari Seldon and Yugo Amaryl were able to develop a plan to reduce the losses from the collapse of the Empire for humanity and the development of a new Empire on the ruins of the old one. This idea was that on a planet remote from the center of the galaxy, not burdened with any resources, a small settlement of scientists, called the Foundation, would be organized, which should subsequently become the center of a future new Empire [4, p. 182]. According to this plan, the period of decline was planned to be reduced from 20,000 years to one millennium. However, the collapse of the Empire led to the technological degradation of the planets surrounding the Foundation, and therefore

the gap in science between them continuously increased. Thanks to the cunning and well-coordinated work of some heads of the Foundation, the future center of the empire manages to maintain its neutrality and, moreover, gain influence over the planets that threaten it. Such crises occurred more than once during the development of the Foundation, in the novels they were called Seldon's crises. The result of all these crises, despite their seeming hopelessness, was a hologram of a gray-haired old man, declaring over and over again that all the events that took place were planned in advance and their outcome was predetermined.

Gradually, the events of the novels moved further and further away from the starting point, more and more factors appeared that were impossible to take into account in advance. Therefore, the science fiction writer took an unexpected step – he introduced the Second Foundation, in which he concentrated psychically gifted people working to improve the science of Psychohistory. The Second Foundation was a direct successor to the idea of Hari Seldon, however, unlike the First Foundation, it did not blindly follow the mathematician's forecasts, but consciously edited his science and modified it as it developed. The Second Foundation gives a clear definition of the term psychohistory: “Psychohistory is more extensive than history, the observer's view of the interaction of people's actions, their spiritual (mental) path and consciousness, with their natural and mental (spiritual) environment. Must have a greater degree of knowledge of the development of civilizations than any other discipline. The essence of the existence of psychohistory is in predicting the likely future directions for the development of communities and influencing them at key points, to help in choosing the right path for further development” [5, p. 11]. The Second Foundation, despite its apparent omnipotence, was only a fixer that did not allow the First Foundation to deviate from the original precepts of Hari Seldon.

Numerous disputes arose regarding the content of Isaac Asimov's novels – not all people agreed with the ideas of the science fiction writer, relying on their superficiality and bias. As a result, this forced the author to express himself about his work: “I would like to consider psychohistory in essence, as a science invented

by me. It was, in a sense, a struggle between free will and determinism... Throughout the cycle, we will observe the confrontation between the power of personal desire and that dead hand of general inevitability” [5, p. 12].

After reading the work of Isaac Asimov, many people wondered if long-term forecasting is possible at all, because progress in our time does not stand still, and man is constantly evolving. Throughout history, each new generation of people makes its own adjustments to the moral and ethical assessment of what is happening in society, i.e. mores in society change with each generation. On this occasion, a separate rule has even been formed in history, called the principle of historicism, which says that in relation to the past it is impossible to apply the modern worldview. Exactly the same rule applies to the future. Therefore, due to the fact that we do not have knowledge about the future, it is impossible to predict changes in mores, and therefore accurate predictions of the future are impossible. On the other hand, the model of relations between people, despite external changes, remained exactly the same as it was in the days of Ancient Rome. This question is purely debatable; in our opinion, it is impossible to give a clear and unambiguous answer to it.

The ideas of Isaac Asimov the writer and his conclusions made by the author are quite tangible and have a solid foundation under them. Many ideas of synergetics, a promising direction of scientific thought today, are reflected in these books. It is not at all necessary to talk about historical research inspired by this cycle of works: dozens of scientific papers, many books and a whole trend in history called cliodynamics were born thanks to the work of Isaac Asimov. There are currently about 300 psychohistory or cliometry research teams in the United States. At the same time, the GDELT project is being funded by DARPA [6, p. 3]. The essence of the project is to digitize all historical events and processes, divided into 300 categories. The project currently covers a quarter of a billion events. Serious research in psychohistory and cliodynamics are held at the Institute of Applied Mathematics named after Keldysh, by teams of G. Malinetsky, A. Grinev, A. Korotaev and others.

Conclusion. Isaac Asimov largely anticipated the vector of development of social thought, but his works had many reservations that did not allow us to literally

project the author's thoughts onto objective reality. However, as a literary world that lives according to its own internal laws, the universe of the Foundation is an example to follow. Isaac Asimov's inherent sense of the internal logic of what is happening is played out here in full: the world only once globally adjusts to the needs of the writer, and this change is well explained by the author. As the cycle was written, the writer moved further and further away from psychohistory, gradually this science becomes not a concept that the novel describes, but a trigger that pushes plot events in the right direction. In its place came the metaphysical reasoning of the writer, and the tone of the work changed somewhat. We believe that it was for this reason that the author did not want to put an end to his epic and Seldon's plan was never completed. The writer withdrew from the completion of this epic, having gone into writing the prehistory of the emergence of the Foundation, leaving the reader a vast field for reflection.

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